

Decision Support System for Tourism in Northern Part of Thailand

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Abstract : The purposes of this study were to design and find users' satisfaction after using the decision support system for tourism in the Northern part of Thailand, which can provide tourists with touristic information and plan their personal voyage. Such information can be retrieved systematically based on personal budget and provinces. The samples of this study were five experts and users: 30 "white collars" in Bangkok. This decision support system was designed via ASP.NET. Its database was developed by using MySQL, for administrators to effectively manage the database. The application outcome revealed that the innovation works properly as sought in objectives. Specialists and white collars in Bangkok have evaluated the decision support system; the result was satisfactorily positive.

Keywords : decision Support System, ASP.NET, MySQL, white collars

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